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Methanol Oxidation Reaction on Platinum Catalysts Deposited onto Ceria-Carbon Substrate

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Abstract

Since scientists around the world are looking for strategies to reduce pollutions from mobile vehicles and fossil fuel combustion, many potential solutions are offered for electric cars such as batteries, supercapacitors and hydrogen-gas fuel cells. However, those solutions have barriers for commercialization. Therefore, there is room for direct alcohol fuel cells (DAFC), which generate higher energy density than hydrogen-gas fuel cells and low CO₂ emission compared with fossil fuel combustion. The greatest challenges for DAFC commercialization are stability and price. That leads to this study which focuses on improving stability and reducing price of catalyst materials for DAFCs by the synthesis of novel catalyst materials with low loading of platinum nanoparticles.

Since the fluorite structure of ceria provides high amount of oxygen vacancies for high power performance fuel cells and the synergistic effect of cerium with platinum nanoparticles can eliminate the poison of CO-like intermediates on the active platinum sites, this study attempts to optimize the synthesis pathways of Pt/CeO₂-C materials, in which C is Ketjenblack (EC-300J, FuelCellStore) carbon. The CeO₂-C particles were directed to flower shapes by employing histidine during a solvothermal synthesis method. Pt nanoparticles were deposited onto CeO₂-C with different ethylene glycol reduction parameters such as sonication time, microwave, refluxing time and sodium hydroxide concentration. Three Pt/CeO₂-C materials were obtained, PtCe-1, PtCe-2 and PtCe-3.

For material characterization, X-ray diffractograms confirm the presence of CeO₂ and Pt in the materials. From Scherrer analysis, CeO₂ crystallite size is around 16 nm and platinum crystallite size is 2.4-6 nm. Thermogravimetric analysis confirms 19 wt% Pt and 10 wt% CeO₂ presented in PtCe-2. Electrochemical measurements, which were performed in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ and 1 mol dm⁻³ CH₃OH, demonstrate that the PtCe-2 is the most active material. Electrochemical active area of PtCe-2 reaches 41 m_{Pt}² g_{Pt}⁻¹, the cathodic current peak in cyclic voltammetry at the scan rate 0.01 V s⁻¹ is 275 A g_{Pt}⁻¹, and the current in chronoamperometry at 0.5 V vs. RHE is stable at 0.42 A g⁻¹ after 30 minutes. The results agree and are comparable with other study.

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Introduction

Direct methanol fuel cells (DMFC) are promising technologies for energy stationary generators and vehicles having higher energy density generation than hydrogen-gas technology and low CO₂ emission compared with fossil fuel combustion [1]. However, DMFC technology has also many barriers, e.g. poor kinetics at both anode [2] and cathode [3]. At the anode side, intermediates of methanol oxidation such as CO, formic acid, and formaldehyde poison the platinum active side and impede the Pt catalytic activity [4]. Therefore, the dissociative adsorption of water on Pt active site to produce oxygenated species is critical to oxidize the CO-like and refresh the Pt site [1]. Unfortunately, the dissociative adsorption happens at high anodic potential (> 0.75 V) on Pt [1]. Therefore, the addition of other metals, to act as a second functional site promotor, is necessary for weakening the adsorptive strength of CO-like intermediates at the Pt sites and increasing the CO-like intermediate oxidation[5–8].

CeO₂ possesses a fluorite-structured oxide with high oxygen storage capacity with its rich oxygen vacancies and low redox potential between Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ [9]. The first benefit of CeO₂ is to adjust oxygen concentration at the catalyst surface under the reaction condition, and work as an oxygen buffer [10]. Therefore, CeO₂ can be used as a co-catalyst with various catalysts such as Pt/C [11], PtRu/C [12], Pd/C [6] and PdNi/C [7] in the anode for the low-temperature direct alcohol fuel cell. In the solvothermal synthesis with urea, the flower shaped CeO₂ possesses higher porosity and oxygen vacancy content than nanorod shapes [8]. The CeO₂ synthesized using histidine (His) possesses an urchin flower-like shape while, in case of using proline and valine, the CeO₂ particles were nanorod shapes[5].

In a comparison of CeO₂-Pt/C and Pt/C, the optimal composition of CeO₂-Pt/C proved higher activity and stability for DMFC [6,9,11]. The presence of 4f electrons in the ground state of CeO₂ can transfer to the Pt 3d orbital. That electron effect may change the Pt structure and weaken the adsorption strength of CO-like intermediates. In the result, the CO-like coverage decreases on the Pt surface and initiates the oxidation of intermediates [9]. However, CeO₂-Pt/C with histidine, so-called His-CeO₂-Pt/C, obtained 1.5 times higher mass activity than CeO₂-Pt/C [13]. It was explained by three factors. Firstly, more oxygen vacancies to provide sufficiently OH_{ads} on the surface, and thereby the elimination of the CO_{ads} on Pt surface. The strong interactions between the Pt species and His-CeO₂ accelerate the elimination of intermediate poisons, explained by the CO_{ads} diffusion onto the Pt-CeO₂ interface and oxidized by the OH_{ads} species[1,13,14]. Additionally, the His-CeO₂ material helps to increase the number of metallic Pt species and produce the small Pt nanoparticles during the platinum deposition.

1. Scientific Approach

This study aims to improve the ethylene glycol reduction method for platinum nanoparticle deposition by interfering the production of glycolate ions. Platinum nanoparticles were deposited onto His-CeO₂-C substrate with various parameters such as sonication time, microwave, refluxing time, and sodium hydroxide concentration. The catalyst materials were characterized by X-ray diffraction and thermogravimetric analysis. Electrochemical measurements with cyclic voltammetry, chronoamperometry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ electrolyte were performed, and the methanol oxidation reaction activity was measured with the addition of 1 mol dm⁻³ CH₃OH.

2. Experiments

Preparation of Histidine-CeO₂-C

In the preparation, L-histidine (Sigma-Aldrich, ≥99% purity) is employed to control the growth of CeO₂ particles. This synthesis is modified from the guide of Atla et al. [5]. The mixture of His-CeO₂ is calculated to be 19 wt. % and 81 wt. % of Ketjenblack carbon (C). Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O is used as precursor for CeO₂. The mole of Ce³⁺ ion concentration is taken 2 times higher than the mole of L-histidine concentration in the mixture [5]. Firstly, the mixture of Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O, L-histidine, and carbon is wetted in 1 cm⁻³ of ethanol and is sonicated for 1 hour. After drying overnight at 60 °C, 0.18 mol dm⁻³ of urea solution is poured into the mixture. The urea solvothermal reaction implemented at 130 °C for 12 hours inside a stainless-steel autoclave. After washing the obtained powder multiple times with Milli-Q water and ethanol, the powder is dried overnight at 100 °C. Then, the powder is calcinated at 550 °C for 5 hours under argon gas environment. The final obtained powder is His-CeO₂-C.

Deposition of platinum nanoparticles

Hexachloroplatinic acid hexahydrate, H₂PtCl₆·6H₂O (99.9%, Alfa Aesar), was used as platinum precursor. To optimize the ethylene glycol (EG) reduction method for platinum deposition, platinum nanoparticles were deposited onto His-CeO₂-C substrate by microwave assisted and/or refluxing method. Different factors have been changed for 3 catalyst materials synthesized (PtCe-1, PtCe-2 and PtCe-3) and were listed in the Table 1. Platinum precursor is dissolved into 1 mL of Milli-Q water and transferred together with His-CeO₂-C and EG into the synthesis flask. The sodium hydroxide solution was added into the mixture of the material PtCe-1 and PtCe-2 before sonication, while, in case of the material PtCe-3, the sodium hydroxide solution is added at the last 5 minutes of sonication time. Mixture is sonicated for 1 hour, microwaved to reach the boiling point of the mixture, and refluxed at 125 °C before the mixture was filtrated and rinsed multiple times with Milli-Q water. The powder obtained after filtration and rinsing was dried overnight at 100 °C under 50 mbar vacuum condition. Finally, the platinum catalysts were obtained.

Table 1. Synthesis parameters of catalyst materials

Materials	Nominal Pt content / %	C _{NaOH} / mol dm ⁻³	Water:EG ratio	Add NaOH before / at the end of sonication	Sonication time / minutes	Microwave time / s	Reflux time / hours
PtCe-1	20	0.7	20:40	Before	60	0	4
PtCe-2	26	0.043	2:60	Before	60	78	2
PtCe-3	26	0.15	2:60	At the end	60	81	2

X-Ray diffraction

The X-ray diffractograms for materials in this study are measured by A Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer system coupled with Ni-filtered Cu K α radiation, which consists of 0.6 mm wide parallel beam, two 2.5° Soller slits and LynxEye line detector system. The experiment was conducted with scanning step of 0.01° for 2 θ angle and in the range from 10° to 90°. The total counting time per step was 166 seconds.

Thermogravimetric analysis

In thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), the instrument NETZSCH STA449F3 coupled with Al₂O₃ pan were employed to conduct the experiment for materials studied. The temperature range varied from 25 °C to 1000 °C and the material was heated up at the rate of 10 K min⁻¹ under the gas stream of 40 cm³ min⁻¹ N₂ gas (Linde Gas, 99.999%) and 10 cm³ min⁻¹ O₂ gas (Linde Gas, 99.999%).

Electrochemical measurement

A 3-electrode system was used for electrochemical measurements. For the measurement, the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) connected to the measuring cell via a Luggin capillary was used as a reference electrode, graphite fibre tube electrode (auxiliary electrode) and the working electrode. The working electrode was prepared by covering a 7- μ L drop of catalyst suspension onto a glassy carbon disc electrode with the nominal concentration of 18 μ g_{Pt} cm⁻². The catalyst material suspension was prepared by sonicating materials studied with a mixture of Milli-Q water, isopropanol and Nafion (isomer/carbon ratio ~0.5). All the measurements were carried out using Autolab PGSTAT 204 potentiostat and Nova 1.11.2 software. Before electrochemical measurement, the conditioning procedure was carried out in order to wet and clean the catalyst layer. The conditioning procedure was performed in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution saturated with argon gas (Linde Gas, 99.999%) at 0.5 V s⁻¹ for 100 cycles at the rotating speed 1600 rpm for the working electrode and in the potential range from 0.025 V to 1.4 V.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) at various potential scan rates (0.01-0.4 V s⁻¹) in the potential measuring range from 0.06 V to 1 V was conducted in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution saturated with argon gas.

The methanol oxidation reaction is performed by a CV measurement at 0.01 V s⁻¹ in the potential range from 0.06 V to 1.1 V with the addition of 1 mol dm⁻³ CH₃OH into 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution saturated with argon gas. Chronoamperometry measurements were performed at a fixed potential 0.5 V for 1800 seconds with the interval of 0.5 seconds in the 1 mol dm⁻³ CH₃OH and 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution saturated with argon gas.

3. Results

X-ray diffraction

The diffractogram confirms the presence of platinum nanoparticles and ceria in catalyst materials. The diffractogram of the material His-Ceria-C in Fig. 1 confirmed the presence of cerianite phase, and there is no other structural phase of cerium presented in the material His-CeO₂-C. The PtCe materials has the diffraction peaks of cerianite phase at 2 θ angles

29°, 33°, 47°, 56°, 25°, 59°, 69°, 77°, 79° and 88°, which correspond to the *hkl* planes of ceria (111), (200), (220), (311), (222), (400), (331), (420) and (422), respectively [15]. There is no presence of intermediate cerium products such as cerium oxide carbonate hydrate and cerium carbonate hydroxide. That indicates the complete calcination and success of the synthesis.

Fig. 1. X-ray diffractograms measured for different materials (noted in the figure). The orange dash lines indicate platinum *hkl* planes and the black dash lines demonstrate CeO₂ *hkl* planes which are (111), (200), (220), (311), (222), (400), (331), (420) and (422) from low to high 2 θ diffraction angles.

The diffraction peaks of platinum is presented in the diffractograms for all platinum planes, 2 θ = 40°, 46°, 68°, 82° and 86° for *hkl* planes (111), (200), (311), (331) and (222) [16], respectively. However, the platinum diffraction peaks of the material PtCe is less pronounced and invisible at higher diffraction 2 θ angle values. The characteristics of platinum diffraction peaks of the material PtCe-1 is sharper comparison with PtCe-2.

According to Scherrer analysis, the cerianite crystallite sizes for PtCe-1, PtCe-2 and PtCe-3 materials are 16, 16 and 15 nm. The platinum crystallite size for PtCe-1, PtCe-2 and PtCe-3 materials are 6.1, 2.4 and 2.4 nm, respectively.

Thermogravimetric analysis

The thermogravimetric analysis (Fig. 2) indicates that the moisture content of materials studied is less than 1%. The residual mass at the end of the measurement is 27.4 %, 28.7 %, 18.9 %, 12.7 % and 13.8 % for PtCe-1, PtCe-2, PtCe-3, pre-His-Ceria-C (before calcination) and His-Ceria-C (after calcination), respectively. These residual mass values were used to estimate ceria and platinum contents for materials studied (Table 2). The ceria content is 9.7 %, 9.8 % and 11.2 % in PtCe-1, PtCe-2 and PtCe-3, respectively.

The difference between the nominal platinum content (Table 1) and the platinum content calculated from TGA results (Table 2) indicates the degree of success of platinum deposition method. These platinum content differences for the PtCe-1, PtCe-2 and PtCe-3 are 2.5 %, 7.1 % and 18.3 %, respectively. In comparison with the PtCe-1 and PtCe-2, the failure in the synthesis for the PtCe-3 material is identified as the step of adding NaOH solution at the

end of sonication. Therefore, the longer sonication time with NaOH solution is, the larger platinum particle amount is deposited. In the ethylene glycol reduction in sodium hydroxide system, the formation of glycolate form is necessary for the reduction to the crystal metal [17]. Instead of heating to the near boiling point of ethylene glycol, a long period of sonication with sodium hydroxide seems to achieve the same effect of breaking a hydrogen bond at one site of ethylene glycol.

Fig. 2. The mass change of catalyst materials determined by thermogravimetric analysis.

The first significant mass loss of the pre-His-Ceria-C material at roughly 280 °C is the result of the decomposition of histidine [18]. There is no significant mass loss at the same temperature for the PtCe materials and the His-Ceria-C material. This indicates that there is no presence of histidine anymore on the surface of the His-Ceria-C and PtCe materials, so probably, histidine was fully decomposed during calcination process of His-Ceria-C. The second significant mass loss of the His-Ceria-C material is caused by the decomposition of Ce(CO₃)OH and Ce(CO₃)₂O·H₂O to CeO₂[19].

Electrochemical measurement

The gravimetric capacitance of materials studied, electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) and diameter of spherical particles (d_{ECSA} from the ECSA data) values of platinum were calculated from cyclic voltammetry data in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ (Fig. 3). The hydrogen adsorption/desorption peaks are pronounced in the potential region from 0.06 V to 0.3 V. The electric double layer (EDL) capacitance value is determined from the capacitance minimum |C| in the potential region from 0.3 V to 0.5 V. The increase of capacitance in the potential region from 0.7 V to 1 V (anodic scan) indicates formation of the cover of a oxide monolayer on the Pt surface. This surface oxide layer is reduced during the cathodic scan. The influence of potential scan rate on capacitance is exhibited in the Fig. 3B. In general, the capacitance values |C| increase slightly when the scan rate increases. However, the hydrogen adsorption/desorption peaks at different scan rates are almost at the same potential value and the minimum capacitance values in the electrical double layer region in anodic scan are also constant at 0.4 V.

The capacitance behaviour of materials studied is illustrated in Fig. 3A. The hydrogen adsorption/desorption peaks of the PtCe-2 material are more pronounced and sharper than the other two materials studied. The capacitance values in the region of EDL are higher for PtCe-2 and PtCe-3. This may be caused by the fast-localized heating of microwave, which can generate more defects on carbon surface, applied. The capacitance in the EDL region for material PtCe-3 is also increased because of the higher amount of the carbon in the catalyst. The *ECSA* values of materials studied (Table 2) are consistent with capacitance behaviours in Fig. 3A. The PtCe-2 material possess highest *ECSA* value, which is roughly 1.7 and 3.3 times higher than *ECSA* values of the PtCe-3 and PtCe-1 materials, respectively. The *d_{ECSA}* values are much higher than crystallite size calculated from the Scherrer's formula (Table 2).

Fig. 3. The gravimetric capacitances of materials were calculated from CV data measured in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ (A). The dependence of capacitances on scan rates is demonstrated for the PtCe-2 material (B).

Methanol oxidation reaction

The results of methanol oxidation reaction in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ + 1 mol dm⁻³ CH₃OH are presented in the Figure 4A. The *i*-*E* curves possess two peaks: peak of the anodic (*i_{anodic peak, MOR}*) and cathodic (*i_{cathodic peak, MOR}*) scan. These peak currents are influenced by the platinum surface coverage effect during the CV measurement. The anodic current peak exhibits the coverage of an oxide film on platinum surface while the cathodic current peak indicates the reduction of OH_{ads} species at platinum surface by oxygen reduction reaction in the cathodic potential scan [14]. According to Chung *et al.* [14], the adsorption of CO-like intermediates on the catalyst surface happens in the region from 0.4 V to 0.5 V vs. RHE. The hump at around 0.75 V is the oxidation of CO-like intermediates on the catalyst surface to CO₂ product and the increase of OH_{ads} coverage after that.

The hysteresis of the MOR current peaks is unclear; however, the ratio of the anodic current peak and the cathodic current peak indicates the degree of oxophilicity of the catalysts[14]. The greater the magnitude of the cathodic current peak is, the higher number of free platinum sites on the surface is (Table 2). The oxide coverage and the number of free platinum sites is highest for the PtCe-2 material, which also possesses highest number

of oxygenated groups on the surface in comparison with other two materials. The anodic current peak values for PtCe-1 and PtCe-3 are similar, 135 A g_{Pt}⁻¹ and 128 A g_{Pt}⁻¹, respectively. Surprisingly, the number of free platinum sites (according to $i_{\text{cathodic peak, MOR}}$) for PtCe-1 seems higher than for PtCe-3 although ECSA value of PtCe-3 is greater than PtCe-1. Comparison of PtCe-1 and PtCe-3 shows that large difference in platinum content does not to affect the OH_{ads} coverage, however the number of free platinum sites is apparently different. That leads to the slight difference in chronoamperometry results (Fig. 4B) of PtCe-1 and PtCe-3. Although the PtCe-1 and PtCe-2 materials have approximately the same platinum content, these materials exhibit extreme differences in oxophilicity degree and MOR activity. This is connected to the differences in platinum crystallite size and agglomeration of platinum particles of two materials.

Fig. 4. The methanol oxidation reaction activity is examined by cyclic voltammetry (A) and chronoamperometry (B).

Chronoamperometric results (Fig. 4B and Table 2) at 0.5 V in $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ CH}_3\text{OH}$ agree well with CV results for MOR. The PtCe-2 material was the best material and the current ($i_{0.5 \text{ V, chro}}$) of the PtCe-2 material was stable after 30 min at $0.42 \text{ A g}_{\text{Pt}}^{-1}$ and comparable with the work of Valk *et al.*[20], where the EG-5 material has $\text{ECSA} = 45 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, $d_{\text{ECSA}} = 6 \text{ nm}$, $i_{0.5 \text{ V, chro}} = 0.41 \text{ A g}_{\text{Pt}}^{-1}$. The current ($i_{0.5 \text{ V, chro}}$) of the PtCe-1 and PtCe-3 after 30 min are lower: $0.16 \text{ A g}_{\text{Pt}}^{-1}$ and $0.11 \text{ A g}_{\text{Pt}}^{-1}$, respectively.

It is apparent that the PtCe-2 with lowest ratio of $i_{\text{anodic peak, MOR}}/i_{\text{cathodic peak, MOR}}$ achieves the best performance for MOR. The CA results of PtCe-1 and PtCe-3 materials for MOR also agree with the oxophilicity degree deduced from the CV results. This may be explained by the intrinsic effect and bifunctional mechanism of Pt-CeO₂, in which, oxygenated groups on the surface can oxidize CO-like intermediates desorbed from Pt sites more easily [9]. Since the hump at 0.75 V (Fig. 4A) is apparently present for all materials, the electron effect of CeO₂ may be not strong enough to clearly weaken the adsorption intensity of CO-like intermediates. Thus, it might be taken under consideration to increase the CeO₂ content to have a stronger synergistic effect with platinum. The materials synthesized in high sodium hydroxide concentration exhibit low MOR and low oxophilicity degree.

Table 2. Calculated parameters from thermogravimetric analysis, X-ray diffraction and electrochemical measurements

Material	Pt content (TGA) / %	ECSA / m _{Pt} ² g _{Pt} ⁻¹	d _{Pt} ^{ECSA} / nm	d _{Pt} ^{Scherrer} / nm	i _{anodic peak, MOR} / A g _{Pt} ⁻¹	i _{cathodic peak, MOR} / A g _{Pt} ⁻¹	i _{anodic peak, MOR} / i _{cathodic peak, MOR}	i _{0.5 V, chro} / A g _{Pt} ⁻¹
PtCe-1	17.7	12	23	6.1	135	131	1.03	0.16
PtCe-2	18.9	41	6.9	2.4	230	275	0.83	0.42
PtCe-3	7.7	24	12	2.4	128	100	1.29	0.11

4. Conclusion

Different parameters in ethylene glycol reduction method for platinum deposition have been applied in this study and revealed significant effects on platinum content recovery and material characteristics. The sonication time with sodium hydroxide contributed significantly to platinum deposition. Besides, the microwave effect may generate more defects on the surface. The harmonization effect of sodium hydroxide concentration, sonication time and microwave time seems to influence the formation of oxygenated groups onto the material surface. However, too high sodium hydroxide concentration during ethylene glycol reduction reduces the MOR activity of catalysts.

The differences in oxophilicity degree of the materials directly affect the MOR activity while the difference in platinum content contributes slightly to the MOR activity. The oxygenated groups on the surface contribute to a better performance on MOR which is very well demonstrated by the PtCe-2 material. However, the platinum crystallite size and the agglomeration of platinum particles contribute dominantly to MOR performance.

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